

K-CC-MoCo: A fast respiratory motion correction in coil-compressed K-space for highly accelerated first-pass perfusion cardiac MRI

Elisa Moya-Sáez¹, Rosa-María Menchón-Lara¹, Javier Sanchez-Gonzalez², Rita G. Nunes³, Carlos Real⁴, Carlos Galán-Arriola⁴, Borja Ibanez⁴, Teresa M. Correia^{5,6}, and Carlos Alberola-López¹

¹Laboratorio de Procesado de Imagen, University of Valladolid, Valladolid, Spain.

²Philips Healthcare Iberia, Madrid, Spain.

³Institute for Systems and Robotics – Lisboa and Department of Bioengineering, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal.

⁴Spanish National Centre for Cardiovascular Research, Madrid, Spain.

⁵Center of Marine Sciences-CCMAR, Faro, Portugal.

⁶School of Biomedical Engineering and Imaging Sciences, King's College London, UK.

Motivation: Motion correction in free-breathing first-pass perfusion cardiac MRI (FPP-CMR) is usually done in the image domain, requiring initial reconstruction. This hinders its use in model-based and deep-learning reconstructions from highly accelerated acquisitions.

Goal: To estimate and correct respiratory motion in free-breathing FPP-CMR directly in k-space.

Approach: We propose an inter-frame rigid motion correction formulated in k-space with the normalized-cross-correlation objective function. An ROI-based coil-compression approach was employed to focus the optimization on the heart. The method was tested using a digital phantom and real free-breathing acquisitions with different accelerations.

Results: The proposed approach outperforms image-based correction in acquisitions with accelerations up to 50x.

Impact: The k-space-based motion correction outperforms image-based correction in free-breathing FPP-CMR acquisitions accelerated up to 50x. This method can estimate/correct respiratory motion in k-space without an initial reconstruction, thereby enabling its use for model-based and/or deep-learning reconstructions from highly accelerated scans.

Purpose

First-pass perfusion cardiac MRI (FPP-CMR) enables non-invasive diagnosis of ischemic heart disease by capturing a sequence of images during the rapid passage of a contrast bolus through the heart¹. Traditionally, patients are instructed to hold their breath to reduce blurring and misalignments caused by respiratory motion, although residual motion caused from inadequate breath-holding usually arises. However, there is a growing preference to acquire images during free-breathing due to increased reliability and patient comfort¹. Consequently, the integration of motion correction (MoCo) approaches becomes crucial.

Typically, MoCo in FPP-CMR is formulated in the image domain²⁻⁴ using multimodal metrics to deal with the dynamic contrast. However, model-based and deep-learning reconstruction methods, which enable high acceleration factors (AFs), cannot directly use these methods^{5,6}. Alternatively, motion could be estimated/corrected directly in k-space avoiding the need for an initial reconstruction and potentially enabling increased performance at high AFs. In this work, we propose K-CC-MoCo: an inter-frame rigid respiratory MoCo for FPP-CMR formulated exclusively on k-space data. The method was tested in a digital phantom and 10 patients for different AF.

Methods

Approach

The proposed approach performs pairwise registration to align each frame of the sequence to a common reference (see Figure 1). To avoid variations caused by dynamic contrasts, the normalized-cross-correlation (NCC) was employed as the optimization metric defined between the reference k-space (S_r) and the corrected k-space (S_c):

$$S_c(\mathbf{k}; \Theta) = S_m(\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{k}) e^{j2\pi \Theta_T^T \mathbf{k}},$$

where the rigid transformation is: $\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} \Theta_R \\ \Theta_T \end{bmatrix}$, with $\Theta_R = [\theta_1 \dots \theta_n]^T$ and $\Theta_T = [u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3]^T = [\theta_{n+1} \ \theta_{n+2} \ \theta_{n+3}]^T$ where subscript R stands for rotation and T for translation. Note that we exploit the fact that a rotation and translation of the object in image-space corresponds to a rotation and a linear phase-shift in k-space, respectively. Additionally, rotation is implemented as 3-shears⁷ to avoid interpolation errors in k-space, which lead to image blurring.

Thus, the optimization is:

$$\hat{\Theta} = \arg \min_{\Theta} -|NCC(S_f, S_c(\Theta))|^2,$$

where

$$NCC(S_f, S_c(\Theta)) = \frac{N(\Theta)}{D(\Theta)} = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{k}} S_f(\mathbf{k}) S_c^*(\mathbf{k}; \Theta)}{\sqrt{\sum_{\mathbf{k}} |S_f(\mathbf{k})|^2 \sum_{\mathbf{k}} |S_c(\mathbf{k}; \Theta)|^2}}$$

The optimization was solved with a nonlinear conjugate gradient algorithm with backtracking line search⁸. To focus the cost function on the heart, we used an ROI-based coil-compression (CC) approach to compress k-space into a single virtual coil in which the ROI signal is maximized⁹. Note that respiratory motion implies, to a large extent, a rigid transformation of the heart, although smaller elastic deformations may occur. We used the k-space mean over time as a synthetic reference, enhancing robustness by accurately capturing overall contrast and position. To reduce blurring, we implemented a refining process updating the reference with the mean of the corrected sequence from the previous iteration.

Data

Digital Phantom: fully-sampled FPP-CMR data with respiratory motion was generated with MRXCAT¹⁰ using parameters: 1 slice, 32 frames, FOV=320×320mm², resolution=1.6×1.6mm², slice thickness=5mm, TR/TE/Ts =2/1/150ms, α=15°, and contrast agent relaxivity=5.6L/mmol/s.

Free-breathing FPP-CMR: 10 patients were scanned with IRB approval in an Ingenia 3T MRI scanner (Philips Healthcare, Best, The Netherlands). FPP-CMR acquisition parameters were: 3 slices, ~60/90 frames for REST/STRESS, FOV=300×300mm², resolution=2.6×2.6mm², slice thickness=10mm, TR/TE/Ts=2.45/1.15/80ms, α=15°, scan time=60s, contrast agent relaxivity=3.6L/mmol/s. K-spaces were retrospectively generated from DICOM images.

In both studies, 6 coils were simulated using the MRXCAT¹⁰ sensitivity maps and k-spaces were retrospectively undersampled following a radial (k,t)-sampling with AF ranging from 20x to 50x. The MRXCAT¹⁰ population averaged arterial input function (AIF) was used for the estimation of tracer-kinetic parametric maps.

Evaluation

The number of iterations was empirically set to 1 for the digital phantom and 5 for patient data. Our approach was compared with a robust image-based registration method, pTVreg¹¹, which performed rigid registration of the sum-of-squares reconstructed image. The pTVreg motion estimation from the fully-sampled sequence was considered the ground-truth.

Results

Figure 2 shows, for the digital phantom, the sequences with and without MoCo when motion was estimated from undersampled k-space with different AF. Figure 3 shows K-CC-MoCo compared with pTVreg for a representative patient. Figure 4 shows boxplots of the evaluation metrics for both methods in all patients. Finally, Figure 5 shows the quantitative perfusion maps estimated from k-space data with and without MoCo.

Discussion

K-CC-MoCo was tested using a digital phantom and free-breathing FPP-CMR acquisitions. The proposed k-space-based method is ~2x faster than pTVreg and it can correct respiratory motion even with high AF, such as 50x, whereas the image-based method fails in those cases due to the strong undersampling artifacts. While pTVreg with sum-of-squares reconstruction may misuse coil information, compressed sensing and low-rank methods also suffer from artifacts and temporal blurring at high AFs and require additional reconstruction time. Notably, after K-CC-MoCo, the quantitative maps are visibly less blurred. Future work includes additional validation with prospectively undersampled data to establish clinical applicability.

Conclusion

We propose K-CC-MoCo, an inter-frame rigid respiratory MoCo for free-breathing FPP-CMR formulated in k-space. The results show K-CC-MoCo outperforms image-based correction for highly accelerated acquisitions.

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Figure 1: Proposed pipeline for motion correction in k-space. The undersampled k-space is used for a sum-of-squares (SoS) reconstruction in which an ROI of the heart region is drawn. Next, an ROI-based coil-compression is performed to generate a single virtual coil, in which the signal from the ROI is maximized. Then, the k-space of each frame is registered to the reference (i.e., mean along the k-space dynamics). A refinement with I iterations is performed in which the reference is updated with the mean along the frames of the corrected k-space sequence from the previous iteration $i-1$.

Figure 2: [animation] Digital phantom motion correction (MoCo) for acceleration factors (AFs) 20x and 45x. A) Undersampled k-space data, which is used to estimate motion. B) Fully-sampled (FS) perfusion images without MoCo. C) FS perfusion images with MoCo performed in k-space. D) Intensity profiles in the y-t direction (yellow line, foot-head). Note that the motion is estimated from the undersampled k-space, although the results are shown in the FS images to facilitate visualization.

Figure 3: [animation] Motion correction (MoCo) for acceleration factors (AFs) 30x and 50x for a representative patient. A) Sum-of-squares (SoS) reconstructions from the undersampled k-space data. B) Fully-sampled (FS) dynamic images without MoCo. C) FS dynamic images with K-CC-MoCo. D) FS dynamic images with image-based pTVreg MoCo. E) Intensity profiles in y-t direction (yellow line, foot-head). Motion is estimated from the undersampled k-space in C) and from the SoS image in D), but results are shown in the FS images to facilitate visualization.

Figure 4: Boxplots of the structural similarity index measure (SSIM) and mean squared error (MSE) computed for the fully-sampled (FS) images with K-CC-MoCo, and the FS images with pTVreg (i.e., image-based motion correction). In both cases, the metrics were calculated with respect to the FS images with ground-truth (GT) motion correction. Motion was estimated from undersampled data corresponding to an acceleration of 50x. Statistically significant differences were found between the two methods ($p = 0.007$) with a Wilcoxon signed rank test.

Figure 5: Quantitative maps ($KTrans$) obtained from the REST fully-sampled (FS) perfusion image sequences with and without motion correction (MoCo) for 3 representative patients. A) Quantitative maps obtained with the ground-truth (GT) MoCo in which motion was estimated from the FS image. B) Quantitative maps obtained without MoCo. C) Quantitative maps obtained with K-CC-MoCo. In C), motion was estimated from the 50x accelerated undersampled k-space.